

Research Project

Visualization and analysis on changes in case governments for verbs *alkaa* and *pystyä*: 1st infinitive or 3rd infinitive?

1 Background and research questions

In 2024, Institute for the Languages of Finland (Kotimaisten Kielten Keskus, hereafter referred to as Kotus) officially accepted “*alkaa + 3rd infinitive (hereafter referred to as *alkaa+ill*)*” as a standard expression in Finnish, before which the only correct and long-standing case government in formal language was “*alkaa + 1st infinitiivi (hereafter referred to as *alkaa+infl*)*”. This historical decision was driven by the significant prevalence of the case government of the 3rd infinitive used both in spoken and official texts contemporarily. It is an explicit example for the phenomena that languages are always changing and this change is natural. It also shows that the standardized language is not always fixed and it could be changed under the influences of language usage.

Having new variations of case government for the verb “*alkaa*” is not the only case. Kotus’s volunteer observation (*Talkoohavaintoja I*) has noticed a similar trend in verbs, which express the meanings of necessities and possibilities, for instance, *joutua*, *pyrkää*, and *kyetä*.

Here I take the verb *pystyä* as an example for its high appearance in spoken and written Finnish. According to current standard Finnish grammar rules, the verb *pystyä* governs the 3rd infinitive, but Kotus has noticed the following non-standard variations in both spoken and written language:

1. *pystyä tehdä (pystyä + infl)*
2. *pystyä tekee(n)*: derived from *pystyä + tekemään*, but *ma/mä* is truncated and the letter *n* in the end is sometimes dropped off.

Driven by the phenomena and trends of changing case governments in verbs, my data-driven research questions are as follows:

1. How did structures “*alkaa + infl*” and “*alkaa + ill*” evolve and change over time before and after its standardization on official and unofficial platforms?
2. How did structures “*pystyä + infl*” and “*pystyä + ill*” evolve and change over time within the same time on official and unofficial platforms?
3. How do these two curves compare with each other?

2 Data collection and processing

To extract concordances and frequencies with time stamps, I chose to use Korp platform, which offers rich datasets in Finnish for both official texts, including newspapers and magazines, and unofficial texts, for instance, texts from Suomi24 and Ylilauta.

To better represent language usages in formal and informal platforms, I chose two representative corpora as follows:

1. **For texts from official platforms**, I chose a subcorpus from 1850s to 2020s of Finnish newspapers and magazines of National Library (*Kansalliskirjaston sanoma- ja aikakauslehtikokoelman suomenkielinen osakorpus versio 2, Korp (klk-fi-v2-korp)*), hereafter referred as *KLK*), which contains newspapers and magazines between 1771 and 2021 of the collections in National Library. Considering the continuity of frequency and dates, I used the data ranging from 1850s to 2020s, which more specifically from 1850 to 2021. The corpus is 22.45 G in size.
2. **For texts from unofficial platforms**, I chose a corpus (*Suomi24-keskustelupalvelun keskustelut vuosilta 2001–2023 (1.1.2001–31.12.2023)*), hereafter referred as *Suomi24*), which includes contents of discussion on Suomi24 platform, which was one of the largest internet discussion platforms in Finland and interaction analyses have been conducted on the data collected from Suomi24 by scholars from University of Jyväskylä. The size of the corpus is 5.06G.

Due to different sizes of corpora, I decided to compare with relative frequencies. To search for relative frequencies for two verbs of different case governments, I used the extended search function in Korp.

For the case government of the 1st infinitive, I set the query by filling different verbs as:
baseform is alkaa/pystyä (case-insensitive); part of speech is verb and msd contains inf1 (case-insensitive).

For the case government of 3rd infinitive, I set the query as
baseform is alkaa/pystyä (case-insensitive); part of speech is verb and msd contains ill (case-insensitive)

The image shows two screenshots of the Korp search interface. The left screenshot shows a search query for 'base form is alkaa/pystyä' with a dropdown menu for 'is' and a search button. The right screenshot shows a search query for 'part of speech is verb and msd contains inf1' with dropdown menus for 'is', 'verb', 'msd', and 'contains', and a search button.

After applying queries in corpora, I exported relative frequencies by using the function “export relative frequency as CSV files” under “Statistics”. I examined the files and manually separate dates and relative frequencies into plain text files as raw data. To prepare for statistical analysis, I processed the raw data into the format of “year, structure, relative frequency” per line by using python codes.

Here is an example for aligning structures for raw data extracted from Suomi24 2001-2023 corpus for case government of “*alkaa+inf1*”. I modified the date and frequency alignment parameters of “years” and named the files accordingly. Both raw data files and processed files could be found in the zip in the appendix.

```
# suomi24 data
with open("suomi24_alkaa_inf1_raw.txt", "r", encoding="utf-8") as f:
    suomi24_alkaa_inf1 = f.read()
    suomi24_alkaa_inf1_file = suomi24_alkaa_inf1.split(";")

years5 = range(2001, 2024)
with open("suomi24_alkaa_inf1.txt", "w", encoding="utf-8") as t:
    for i, alkio in zip(years5, suomi24_alkaa_inf1_file):
        text = f"{i},alkaa+inf1,{alkio.strip()}\n"
        t.write(text)
```

Next step, I used pandas and matplotlib toolkits to draw curves with the formatted files. There are four variables in the curves:

1. x-axis refers to “year”
2. y-axis refers to “**relative frequency**” with the unit of per million tokens
3. **verb**, which could be either *alkaa*, marked in blue lines, or *pystyä*, marked in red lines
4. **infinitive cases**, the 1st infinitive is marked as full lines and 3rd infinitive is marked as dotted lines

Here are the codes for drawing curves for the data extracted from Suomi24. I applied the same codes to KLK data by changing the names into KLK accordingly:

```
# Suomi24 curves
## read processed files
df1 = pd.read_csv("suomi24_alkaa_ill.txt", names=["Year", "Structure",
"Relative frequency"])
df2 = pd.read_csv("suomi24_alkaa_inf1.txt", names=["Year", "Structure",
"Relative frequency"])
df3 = pd.read_csv("suomi24_pystya_ill.txt", names=["Year", "Structure",
"Relative frequency"])
```

```
df4 = pd.read_csv("suomi24_pystya_inf1.txt", names=["Year", "Structure",
"Relative frequency"])

df1["Relative frequency"] = pd.to_numeric(df1["Relative frequency"],
errors="coerce")
df2["Relative frequency"] = pd.to_numeric(df2["Relative frequency"],
errors="coerce")
df3["Relative frequency"] = pd.to_numeric(df3["Relative frequency"],
errors="coerce")
df4["Relative frequency"] = pd.to_numeric(df4["Relative frequency"],
errors="coerce")

## draw curves
plt.plot(df1["Year"], df1["Relative frequency"], label="alkaa+ill",
color="blue", ls="--")
plt.plot(df2["Year"], df2["Relative frequency"], label="alkaa+inf1",
color="blue", ls="-")
plt.plot(df3["Year"], df3["Relative frequency"], label="pystya+ill",
color="red", ls="--")
plt.plot(df4["Year"], df4["Relative frequency"], label="pystya+inf1",
color="red", ls="-")

plt.title("Suomi24: alkaa and pystyä case governments changes 2001–2023")
plt.xlabel("Year")
plt.ylabel("Relative frequency")
plt.axvline(x=2014, color="gray", ls="--") # add a marker for 2014, when
alkaa+ill was officially accepted
plt.grid(True)

plt.legend(loc="upper left", bbox_to_anchor=(1.05, 1)) # move legends out of
the curve
plt.show()
```

3 Data analysis

1. Suomi 24

For platform Suomi24, I will analyse the curves by comparing the different infinitive usage for the same verb and comparing relative frequency for different case governments.

Within the time span between 2001 and 2023, the verb *alkaa* with both its case governments and *pystyä+ill* are more frequently used than *pystyä+inf1*. Their relative frequency is higher than 200 times per million tokens and relative frequency remains stable with little fluctuation. The curve shows that these three ways of expression have been widely accepted and used in spoken language on platform Suomi24.

For the verb *alkaa*, the case government with 1st infinitive is more used than 3rd infinitive, as 1st infinitive case government has been considered “standard” for decades and it still remain as the mainstream, but both frequencies are highly, which implied that 3rd infinitive has already been widely accepted and used in spoken language for majority of people, since it was not recognized as “correct” officially.

For the verb *pystyä*, the gap between 1st infinitive and 3rd infinitive is significant. The relative frequency of *pystyä+inf1* stayed at a near-zero level, which could be interpreted as this structure is used only by very few people on this platform and it is not widely accepted and used by majority when the data was collected, while *pystyä+ill* is used at

a much higher frequency. Compared with the structure *alkaa+ill*, the acceptance level of *pystyä+infl* is much lower and it is less likely to be officially accepted and standardized in written language.

2. KLK

For collections of Finnish National Library, I will analyse the curves by comparing the different infinitive usage for the same verb and comparing relative frequency for different case governments. I will also compare changes in trends before and after 2014, when *alkaa+ill* structure was official accepted as correct expression in written language and year 2014 is marked in grey dotted line in the graph.

From 1850 to 2025, the relative frequency of *alkaa+infl* was around 50 times per million tokens and from 1930s there is an increasing trend, despite there is a sharp drop in 1960s. Since 2020, the relative frequency is around 150 times per million tokens. For *alkaa+ill*, its relative frequency stays at a near-zero level before 2014, but there is a slight increasing trend after 2014 shown in the curve.

For the case government of *pystyä+ill*, its relative frequency stays at near-zero level from 1850 to 1925 and since 1925 there is an increasing trend until 1975. Afterwards, the curve stays at the level of 175 times per million tokens. For *pystyä+infl*, its relative frequency is on average 0.01 times per million tokens.

Based on statistics from both platforms, official platforms used grammatically correct and officially accepted case governments for publications and other variations are rarely used. After 2014 there is a slight increasing trend shown in the trend of *alkaa+ill* structure, but this tendency needs more proof and with more data.

4 Possible biases and limitations

- a) **Digitalized sources are biased when they were collected in the first place.** These sources could be collected under certain principles, which could not represent the trend and cause unnoticeable biases.
- b) **Different time spans for both corpora.** The Suomi24 corpus only contains data from 2001 to 2023, but KKK has a wider time span since 1850s. To avoid possible biases, the comparison for time only conducted within its own time span and cross-comparison is not conducted.
- c) **Different sizes of corpora between formal and informal texts.** As there is a significant gap between the sizes of formal and informal texts, I chose to compare only **relative frequencies** to avoid possible biases generated from the size differences.
- d) **The extracted relative frequency may be lower than actual amount.** I applied my query to search for cases that the case government is directly followed by its case government to ensure that the verb governs the certain case. However, adverbs could be added in between, which would lead to lower relative frequencies.
- e) **Research on the structure *pystyä tekee(n)* was not studied in this project.** The middle form may offer information on the changes.

5 Discussion

The goal of the study is to visualization changes relative frequencies for mainstream case governments and naturally evolved case governments of the verb *alkaa* and *pystyä* on official and unofficial platforms. I applied methods of corpus linguistics and computational programming skills in collecting, cleansing and processing extracted data. The project is meant to provide perspectives for studies of examining the concept of “standardized languages”, the evolution of languages in use, and even predicting the future trends of the acceptance of variations of new case governments of verbs.

Due to biases of the research and limited volume of data, the results of the research can only give a preliminary analysis and visualization of the trend in real historical period. The results certify the fact that official platforms will stick to rules of standard, correct

and long-lasting written language, even after the standardization of a certain case governments, there is no significant increase in its usage according to this result. On unofficial platforms language usage is freer and more open to new variations of verb case governments, and this trend may in turn influence the standard language, but the duration of standardization might be centuries until the acceptance of structure is almost as high as the traditional correct structure.

6 References

- Suomen kielen lautakunta. (2014, January 31). *Suomen kielen lautakunta muutti suositusta: myös alkaa tekemään sopii yleiskieleen - Kotus*. Kotus. Retrieved November 23, 2025, from <https://kotus.fi/suomen-kielen-lautakunta-muutti-suositusta-myos-alkaa-tekemaan-sopii-yleiskieleen/>
- Suomen kielen lautakunta. (2014a). *Alkaa tehdä ja alkaa tekemään rinnakkain yleiskielessä - Kielikello*. Kielikello. Retrieved November 23, 2025, from <https://kielikello.fi/alkaa-tehda-ja-alkaa-tekemaan-rinnakkain-yleiskielessa/Talkoohavaintoja-1-Kotus>. (n.d.). Kotus. <https://kotus.fi/kielenhuolto/yleiskieli-jasen-kehitys/yleiskielen-seuranta/talkoohavaintoja-1/>